

Lost in digitalization? Using data as a source for quantitative art history

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Invited speakers: Bárbara Romero Ferrón², Angela Dressen³, Weixuan Li⁴, Folgert Karsdorp⁵

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Abstract

The rapid advancements of data methods and technologies, coupled with the increasing availability of data from museums, researchers, and art-related institutions, open new avenues for applying data analysis to the field of art history. Nevertheless, art historical data are complex artifacts, whose selection reflects the interests of current and past art collectors and curators, and which often rely on uncertain, interpretative, and incomplete information. Furthermore, only a limited part of such data had been digitized. In this context, the open question is how it is possible to conduct faithful and relevant quantitative analyses in the art history sector, given these limits and challenges. This panel aims to address this issue with speakers from an art historical, technical, or mixed background to discuss which adaptations are needed from statistics, biology, and data science to conduct quantitative analyses that are meaningful to advance art historical knowledge.

Keywords: digital art history, structured data, digitalization, survivorship bias, uncertainty, data analysis

Advancements in data methods and technologies, coupled with the increasing availability of data from museums, researchers, and art-related institutions, open new avenues for applying data analysis to the art history sector. Nevertheless, art historical information relies on the experts' reconstruction of the past, which often lead to partial solutions and debatable information. Therefore, the digital translation of such knowledge must consider the depth and fragility of the critical discourse on which it's based. During the digitization process, which concerned the translation of paper catalogs into structured databases, uncategoryable information was often lost, as the critical discourses that led to the final artwork attribution, with the consequence that polished, ordered digital datasets are often an impoverished version of their paper equivalents. On this stack, it should be added that only a small percentage of art museum catalogs have been digitized or made available online¹, and even a smaller portion seeks to restore the lost complexity of critical discourse using ad-hoc models, such as domain

¹ See the *Core Survey 4* made by the Enumerate project in 2017, in which it emerged that participating museums (from Europe) have 33% of their metadata online for general use, and 42% of the digital objects held by the institutions were not available online. Only 38% of the digital collections of participating museums were available through the Europeana portal in 2017. Further information available at:

<https://pro.europeana.eu/page/results>, <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/digital-collections>, and <https://metis-statistics.europeana.eu/en/>. A more recent study of 2020 by the Network of European Museums Organization (NEMO) shows that, among the participating museums, 43.3% of their collections were digitized, and less than half of the digitized objects were available online. See: https://www.nemo.org/fileadmin/Dateien/public/Publications/NEMO_Final_Report_Digitisation_and_IPR_in_European_Museums_WG_07.2020.pdf For an overview on the UK context, see Charlesworth (2025)

ontologies. Often, only the most famous art pieces are digitized and made available online, with a possible effect of reinforcing the canon rather than giving less-known art a visible space (Zhitomirsky-Geffet et al., 2023). Some approaches to overcome this problem consist of relying on further sources, such as exhibition catalogs, which reflect a more comprehensive view of the art appreciated in a certain period of time (Joyeux-Prunel, 2012; Greenwald, 2021). Nevertheless, such sources are not always available or if they are, they remain largely unstructured and non-machine-readable, limiting their utility for large-scale analysis. Besides these issues, the amount of created structured data keeps growing, with some institutions sharing metadata in order of millions of items, making quantitative overviews possible.

Whereas methods for (big) data analysis are available, conducting quantitative analysis, such as distant viewing, on this partial, interpretative data may lead to partial or biased results from an art historical perspective, if its complexity is not thoroughly taken into account. Furthermore, meaningful quantitative analysis in art historical studies requires datasets to be thoroughly described and complex information to be represented in standardized ways.

Museum data are becoming primary research material for art historians, as is the case with most Cultural Heritage data produced across the GLAM sector and thanks to initiatives such as the collections-as-data movement (Padilla et al., 2023). While computationally skilled researchers can draw on an unprecedented volume and variety of data, these resources are also deliberately constrained by individual museums' choices. This is evident, for example, when museums adopt open-access strategies and provide data through query endpoints: in principle, a researcher could access an institution's entire back-end database, yet in practice museums decide which categories are queryable. Additionally, the use of differing standards, ontologies, and data formats across institutions makes it challenging for researchers to assemble a coherent and reliable dataset (Dressen, 2025; Belteki et al., 2025).

In this panel, we aim to address the topic with our speakers, coming from a more narrowly art historical, technical, or mixed background. The challenge is to discuss which adaptations are needed from statistics, biology, and data science to conduct quantitative analyses that are meaningful to advance art historical knowledge, offering insights beyond the scope of traditional, qualitative inquiries.

Participants will be asked to give short presentations on their experience and perspective in impulses of 10 minutes followed by a discussion among the panellists. This will be stimulated by questions from the organizers about their experience with the topic in their projects and fields, such as art market studies, museum and library data collections, and cultural evolution. The final part of the panel will be dedicated to an open Q&A session, inviting the audience to contribute. As well as sharing their experiences, participants will be asked to reflect on the representativeness of their results, how they dealt with the complexity of their source material and the limits of available data, such as its interpretative nature, embedded uncertainty or the presence of survivorship bias, typical for historically-oriented studies. The aim is to initiate a fruitful interdisciplinary conversation with participants from various backgrounds and areas to envision future directions of study in the Digital Art History field, based not only on the current available art pieces, but also on the art lost throughout history.

The schedule can be summarized as it follows:

- Introduction to the topic and presentation of the speakers (10 minutes)
- Impulses of the speakers with examples from their own work (10 minutes each, for a total of 40 minutes)
- Discussion among the panellists (20 Minutes)
- Discussion with the audience (20 Minutes)

In the following paragraphs, we introduce the invited speakers and provide a short description of the impulse they will give to the discussion.

Speaker: Dr. Bárbara Romero Ferrón, Provenance Lab, Leuphana University

Exhibition catalogues function as epistemological instruments that formalise and record phenomena as complex and short-lived as temporary exhibitions and even permanent collections. In the absence of a shared standard for what they should contain, their changing structures and paratexts have reshaped how exhibitions are documented, remembered, studied, and analysed. Each catalogue encodes a particular epistemic stance, revealing how curators, institutions, or committees chose to frame, select, and narrate an ephemeral event. When such materials are digitised and turned into datasets for large-scale and quantitative analysis, they are often translated into data models that privilege uniformity over heterogeneity. Romero Ferrón will present her work on catalogues of the Exposiciones Nacionales de Bellas Artes in Spain from 1856 to 1939, showing how approaching these catalogues as social objects requires reconfiguring the ways we model and quantify them so that their specificities are meaningfully preserved.

Speaker: PD Dr. Angela Dressen, Andrew W. Mellon Librarian for Reference and Research Services, Biblioteca Berenson - I Tatti, The Harvard University Center for Italian Renaissance Studies

Research data are becoming increasingly important across the humanities. For art historians delving into Data Science, the most significant sources come from Cultural Heritage institutions such as museums. These resources enable both large-scale data analysis—useful for statistical approaches and comparative analyses—and highly targeted queries. Yet working with such data presents notable challenges. Beyond the required research and computational skills, difficulties arise from the diversity of cataloging standards, ontologies, and data formats used by different institutions. As a result, researchers cannot rely on a single method that works across databases. Moreover, research questions must be shaped by the data each museum chooses to make available, since access is uneven and selectively curated. Consequently, the current landscape of data-driven art-historical research depends on numerous limiting factors that hinder its full potential.

Speaker: Dr. Weixuan Li, Rijksmuseum

Within art history, knowledge is often marked by uncertainty, which increases as documents on the commission, creation, and circulation of artworks wear away over time. Dating of artworks, for instance, is confined to ranges rather than precise years. When such knowledge is digitised at scale, databases inherit—and sometimes foreground—these uncertainties through their ontologies. For broader discussion, Li asks how we can account for uncertainties while still extracting patterns from large databases. She will bring in, as an example, a probabilistic framework for visualising production over time and reconstructing places of creation for early modern Dutch paintings (Li, 2019, 2024). Using this approach, each work is represented as a probability distribution over years and locations, derived from artists' biographical details. Aggregating these distributions makes it possible to plot city-level production trends without suppressing uncertainty. With this example, Li puts forward the discussion of how quantitative analysis can accommodate uncertain art-historical knowledge instead of being 'lost' in large-scale datasets.

Speaker: Prof. Dr. Folgert Karsdorp, KNAW Meertens Institute, Utrecht University

Folgert Karsdorp's contribution will examine how cultural loss and collector bias shape the evidence on which we base cultural-historical claims. Building on ecological models of unseen diversity and recent extensions that account for heterogeneous survival, he aims to quantify not only how much culture is missing but which kinds of materials are disproportionately lost and why. Coupled with methods for measuring dataset completeness and archival distortion, this work seeks to make loss empirically visible (Karsdorp et. al 2024).

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References

- Belteki, D., Rees, A. J., & Sichani, A.-M. (2025). Datafication and Cultural Heritage Collections Data Infrastructures: Critical Perspectives on Documentation, Cataloguing and Data-sharing in Cultural Heritage Institutions. *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.277>
- Charlesworth, E. M. Z. (2025). UK Museums Online: Digital Inequality, Engagement, and Algorithmic Mediations [Doctoral Thesis, Durham University]. <https://etheses.durham.ac.uk/id/eprint/16488/>
- Dressen, A. (2025). Cultural Heritage Data for Research—An Introduction. *Open Library of Humanities*, 11(1).
- Greenwald, D. S. (2021). *Painting by Numbers*. Princeton University Press.
- Joyeux-Prunel, B. (2012). ARTL@S: A Spatial and Trans-national Art History Origins and Positions of a Research Program. *Artl@s Bulletin*, 1(1).
- Karsdorp, Folgert, Mike Kestemont, and Margo de Koster. 2024. "Beyond the Register: Demographic Modeling of Arrest Patterns in 1879-1880 Brussels." *Proceedings of the Computational Humanities Research Conference, 2024*, 265–81. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3834/paper13.pdf>
- Li, W., 'Innovative Exuberance: Visualizing the fluctuations in painting production in the 17th-century Northern Netherlands', *Arts, Special Issue: Art Markets and Digital Histories*, 2019 8(2), 72. DOI: 10.3390/arts8020072
- Li. W., 'Deep Mapping Uncertain Historical Sources', *Journal for the History of Knowledge, Special Issue Mapping Uncertainties*, 2024(5), 131-152. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.55283/jhk.13998>
- Zhitomirsky-Geffet, M., Kizhner, I., & Minster, S. (2023). What do they make us see: A comparative study of cultural bias in online databases of two large museums. *Journal of Documentation*, 79(2), 320–340. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-02-2022-0047>
- Padilla, T., Scates Kettler, H., & Shorish, Y. (2023). Collections as Data: Part to Whole Final Report. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10161976>